

INTEGRATING STATIC AND DYNAMIC VOTING PROTOCOLS TO ENHANCE FILE AVAILABILITY

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ABSTRACT

There are several consistency control algorithms for managing replicated files in the face of network partitioning due to site or communication link failures. In this paper, we propose a hybrid scheme that integrates the static voting protocol and dynamic voting with linearly ordered copies. We use a stochastic model to compare the file availability afforded by the proposed hybrid scheme against the availabilities of voting, dynamic voting, and dynamic voting with linearly ordered copies. The analysis provides evidence for the conjecture that the hybrid scheme is the *optimal* algorithm in the context of the stochastic model.

I. INTRODUCTION

There are several consistency control algorithms for managing replicated data in the face of network partitioning due to site or communication link failures [1]. *Voting* [2,3,4] is the best known example of such a scheme. More recently, researchers have introduced algorithms that permit a dynamic reassignment of votes [5,6,7,8,9,10,11]. Of these, *dynamic voting with linearly ordered copies* [11], hereafter referred to as *dynamic-linear*, is particularly attractive. It shares two virtues with ordinary voting: it has a simple statement that permits a clear correctness proof, and it is easy to implement. In addition, it has excellent availability.

It was shown in [11] that the file availability afforded by dynamic-linear is greater than the availability of voting if the file is replicated at four or more sites in the network, but ordinary voting is superior if the number of sites that have copies is exactly three. The present work introduces a *hybrid* algorithm. The algorithm is of interest for two reasons. First, it shows how one can merge static and dynamic voting algorithms. Second, it is the leading candidate for the *optimal* algorithm in the context of our homogeneous, stochastic model.

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In Section II, we state the problem more precisely. Section III presents informal descriptions of voting, dynamic voting, dynamic-linear, and our new hybrid algorithm. Section IV illustrates the hybrid algorithm by an example. In Section V, we give a careful description of the hybrid algorithm, with all the details of the protocol spelled out. Section VI contains a stochastic analysis of the availability of the hybrid algorithm.

In sum, this paper makes three original contributions. First, it introduces a hybrid algorithm that combines static and dynamic voting. Second, the paper gives the details of the protocol by which the algorithm operates; these details apply equally well to our other dynamic algorithms [10,11]. Third, the availability of the hybrid algorithm is computed using a stochastic model. The results of this analysis suggest that for all reasonable repair/failure ratios, the hybrid algorithm is the *optimal* algorithm in the context of our homogeneous, stochastic model.

II. FORMAL SPECIFICATION OF THE PROBLEM

The distributed database (DDB) system consists of a collection of independent computers, called *nodes* or *sites*, connected via communication links. We assume that site failures are clean, i.e., nodes stop executing without performing any incorrect actions and that node crashes are detectable by other nodes [12]. We do not include Byzantine failures [13] where sites may act in an arbitrary and malicious manner. Site or communication failures may separate the sites into more than one connected component of communicating sites. We call each connected component a *partition*.

There are several logical files in the DDB, and a physical copy of each logical file is stored at one or more sites. Each site keeps a history of all updates which it performed on a file. We assume that all sites run a *concurrency control protocol* which ensures that the execution of all transactions at any site is serializable [14,15]. A *consistency control protocol* ensures that the replicated data is managed correctly in the presence of failures. (An excellent survey of several of these strategies is given in [1].) In a *pessimistic* consistency control protocol, mutual consistency of a replicated file is maintained by making sure that all

reads and writes are fresh and that files are updated in at most one partition at any given time. We will call such a partition the *distinguished* partition. Different pessimistic protocols use different rules to define the distinguished partition. When site or communication link recoveries cause partitions to unite, the nodes form a new partition by comparing their histories and obtain, if necessary, all updates that they have missed. If there does not exist a distinguished partition, all sites in the system must wait until enough sites and communication links are repaired so that there is once again a distinguished partition in the system. Since this wait is unavoidable [16], the challenge is to come up with a pessimistic consistency control algorithm which not only preserves mutual consistency of various copies of a file, but at the same time achieves high availability as well.

III. INFORMAL DESCRIPTION OF THE ALGORITHMS

Since our protocol does not depend on the number of files that are replicated, we assume for ease of exposition that there a single file f which is replicated at n sites S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n .[†] In this section, we present the algorithms somewhat informally. The next section contains an example, after which we give a very precise explication of the hybrid algorithm.

For voting [2,3,4] in its simplest form, the distinguished partition is the partition, if any, that contains more than half of the sites. Clearly, this meets the second requirement of a pessimistic algorithm: there cannot exist more than a single such partition at any instant. The first requirement (fresh reads and writes) is met by maintaining a version number with each copy of the file.

Ordinary voting is a *static* algorithm, in that all possible distinguished partitions can be listed in advance [17,18]. Recently, several researchers have suggested *dynamic* algorithms that dynamically change the rules for defining the distinguished partition [5,6,7,8,9,10,11]. These algorithms use different mechanisms to accomplish similar ends. For example, the Davcev-Burkhard algorithm [5] requires that each site maintain a connection vector that continuously records the list of sites to which that site can talk. Barbara, Garcia-Molina and Spauster [7,8] present protocols for autonomous reassignment of votes.

Our own dynamic algorithm [10] (which we call simply "dynamic voting") operates by associating with each copy of the file f two integer variables: *version number* and *update sites cardinality*. The update sites cardinality of copy f_i is maintained in such a way that it is always the number of sites that participated in the most recent update to f_i . Thus, if the copy at site A has version number 12 and update sites cardinality 7, then seven sites participated in the update to version 12. The distinguished partition is defined to be the partition, if any, that contains more than half of the *up-to-date* copies of the file. The details of this

[†] Our work generalizes to the setting where transactions may update two or more files. Any such transaction T will require a majority for every file in its read and write set.

protocol can be distilled from the details we present for the hybrid algorithm in Section V. But the basic operation of dynamic voting is simple. A partition P determines whether it is the distinguished partition by first determining the biggest (most recent) version number VN among the copies in partition P , and the update sites cardinality SC of the copies with that version number. Partition P is the distinguished partition iff it contains more than half of the SC sites with version number VN .

The hybrid algorithm we shall shortly describe merges ordinary voting with dynamic-linear [11]. Dynamic-linear extends dynamic voting by adding a third variable, the *distinguished site*. When there are an even number (say SC) of sites participating in an update (say to version VN), each site sets its distinguished site entry to name one of the participating sites. (They can select this site by any mechanism desired, but all the participating sites must select the same site. For example, one might order the sites linearly and select whichever participating site is biggest according to the linear order.) Suppose a subsequent partition finds that version number VN is the most current version among its copies. If this partition contains exactly $SC/2$ sites with version VN , dynamic voting cannot accept the update, for nothing would then prohibit the other half of the SC sites from at the same time doing an update themselves, if they too were grouped in a single partition. Dynamic-linear accepts an update when dynamic voting does, plus also in the case when the partition contains exactly $SC/2$ sites *plus the distinguished site*. That is, the distinguished site is used to "break the tie" when a partition contains exactly half of the sites with the up-to-date version of the file.

The *hybrid* algorithm acts just like dynamic-linear, except as follows.

- (a) When a three-site partition makes an update, the distinguished site entry is expanded to *list* the three sites. This enables the switch from dynamic modification of the distinguished partition to a static, three-site distinguished partition.
- (b) When a partition P wishes to determine whether it is the distinguished partition, it determines as usual the site X that contains the biggest version number in partition P . Suppose the update sites cardinality of site X is 3. In this special case, partition P is the distinguished partition iff it contains two of the three sites on the distinguished sites list of site X . Furthermore, if partition P contains only those two sites, the hybrid algorithm does *not* modify the distinguished partition by changing the update sites cardinality. Only the version number is changed; the hybrid algorithm is in its static phase. However, if partition P contains sites in excess of the required two sites, the algorithm reverts to a mimic of dynamic-linear and dynamically installs P as the new distinguished partition.

The next section presents an example that shows how the hybrid algorithm works. After that we give all the gory details of the protocol.

IV. AN EXAMPLE OF THE HYBRID ALGORITHM

In this example, we assume that the distributed database consists of a single file f which has been replicated at five sites A, B, C, D, and E. These sites are initially connected and form a single partition. Suppose the file f has been updated nine times, so the initial state can be represented as follows where the symbol '-' means that we do not care about the actual value of this variable.

	A	B	C	D	E
VN:	9	9	9	9	9
SC:	5	5	5	5	5
DS:	-	-	-	-	-

At this point suppose site A receives an update, and it finds that it can communicate with sites B and C only. Site A determines that the most current version in its partition is version 9, that the update sites cardinality associated with that version is 5, and that Site A's partition contains three of the five copies with version 9. Site A concludes that it belongs to the distinguished partition and processes the update. Since there are exactly three sites involved in this update, the distinguished site (DS) variables at those participating sites are set to contain their names, in this case ABC. The site cardinalities of the participating sites are each set to 3, since three sites perform the update to version 10. The state then changes to:

	A	B	C	D	E
VN:	10	10	10	9	9
SC:	3	3	3	5	5
DS:	ABC	ABC	ABC	-	-

Suppose now that site A receives yet another update, and it discovers that it can communicate with site C only. The most current version in its partition is version 10, with associated update sites cardinality 3. The novelty here is that since the update sites cardinality is 3, ordinary voting is used to perform the update. Since sites A and C together are two of the three sites on the distinguished sites list, A can process the update. The database state changes to:

	A	C	B	D	E
VN:	11	11	10	9	9
SC:	3	3	3	5	5
DS:	ABC	ABC	ABC	-	-

Note that sites A and C do *not* change their update sites cardinality to 2 (as they would under dynamic voting or dynamic-linear), even though only two sites participated in the update. The hybrid algorithm is in its static phase: the set of potential distinguished partitions is fixed (for the moment) to contain exactly AB, BC, AC, and their supersets. Continuing the example, suppose that now site D receives an update. Suppose it finds that it can communicate with sites B, C, and E. The most current version in this partition is version 11, with associated update sites cardinality 3, so a majority from the three sites on the distinguished sites list is sought. Sites B and C form the desired majority, so the update can take place. (Note that

neither dynamic voting nor dynamic-linear would permit this update.) Since the number of sites in the partition (four) is more than two, the algorithm reenters its dynamic phase and modifies the SC_i entries of the participating sites. Since there are an even number of sites in the distinguished partition, the value of the DS_i variables will be modified as well. Supposing that the sites are ordered in lexicographic order with respect to the file f , and that the distinguished site is selected according to the linear order, DS_i will be set to B at the four sites participating in the update.

	A	B	C	D	E
VN:	11	12	12	12	12
SC:	3	4	4	4	4
DS:	ABC	B	B	B	B

Finally, suppose that the site E were to get an update and finds that it can communicate with site B only. Sites B and E together form a distinguished partition because they contain exactly half of the sites with most-current version number, plus they contain the distinguished site (B). Sites B and E perform the update, leading to the following situation:

	A	B	E	C	D
VN:	11	13	13	12	12
SC:	3	2	2	4	4
DS:	ABC	B	B	B	B

V. THE HYBRID PROTOCOL IN DETAIL

A. Data structures

We assign an a priori total ordering to the sites, denoted by $>$, for the file f . (Different files may be replicated at different groups of sites, and sites in each group may be assigned different total orderings.)

We associate with each copy of the file f three variables: version number, update sites cardinality, and distinguished sites list, defined as follows.

Definition 1. The *version number* of a copy f_i at site S_i is an integer VN_i which counts the number of successful updates to f_i . We set VN_i to zero initially and increment it by one each time an update to f_i occurs.

Definition 2. Associated with each copy f_i at site S_i is another integer called the *update sites cardinality*, denoted by SC_i , which (almost) always reflects the number of sites participating in the most recent update to f_i . We let $SC_i = n$ (number of sites) initially, and whenever an update is made to f_i , then SC_i is set to the total number of copies which were updated during that update. The hybrid nature of our algorithm creates a single exception to this rule, however. See the procedure **Do_Update** below.

Definition 3. We associate with each copy f_i at site S_i a variable called *distinguished sites list*, denoted by DS_i . The value of a DS_i is important iff the corresponding SC_i is even or is equal to 3. When SC_i is even, DS_i identifies the site which is greater (in the linear ordering for the file f) than all other sites that participated in the most recent update to f_i . When $SC_i = 3$, DS_i lists those three sites from which a majority is needed to form a distinguished partition.

B. Protocol under normal operation

In this section, we describe our three-phase protocol, assuming first that no site or communication link failures take place during the execution of these phases; we shall describe in the next section how our scheme adjusts in the face of failures.

Suppose a site S receives an update to the file f . S initiates execution of the protocol consisting of the following three phases[†]:

- (i) S issues a LOCK_REQUEST to its local lock manager.
- (ii) When the lock request is granted, S sends a VOTE_REQUEST message to all the sites.
- (iii) When a site S_j receives a VOTE_REQUEST, it issues a LOCK_REQUEST to its local lock manager. When the lock request is granted, S_j sends to S the values VN_j , SC_j , and DS_j .
- (iv) The site S collects the responses from the various sites and decides if it is a member of a distinguished partition (see routine **Is_Distinguished** below). Henceforth, we refer to S as the *co-ordinator* and the respondents as *subordinates*.
- (v) If S does not belong to a distinguished partition, it aborts the update, issues a RELEASE_LOCK request to its local lock manager, and sends ABORT messages to all the participants. When a participant receives the ABORT message, it too issues a RELEASE_LOCK message to its local lock manager.
- (vi) If S does belong to a distinguished partition, it determines if its copy is current; if it is not current, S determines what subordinates have current copies of the file f . (See routine **Catch_Up** below.) If the copy at site S is current, S proceeds with the next step. Otherwise, S acquires the missing updates from any subordinate that has a current copy, and then continues with the next step.
- (vii) Once the copy at S is current, S reads its copy of the file f and performs the update. Then, S commits the update to the file f together with the modification to its VN_i , SC_i , and DS_i , and sends to each S_j the COMMIT message along with the missing updates (if necessary), the new update to f , and the new values for VN_j , SC_j , and DS_j . Moreover, S issues a

RELEASE_LOCK request to its lock manager. See the procedure **Do_Update** below.

- (viii) Each S_j acts on the message received from S , and then issues a RELEASE_LOCK request to its lock manager.

The three phases of our protocol are: the voting phase (steps (ii) - (v)), the catch-up phase (step (vi)), and the commit phase (steps (vii) and (viii)). Note that the catch-up phase is not necessary if the copy at S is current.

We now describe in more detail each of the three phases in turn. To initiate the voting phase, the site S executes the **Is_Distinguished** procedure described below.

Is_Distinguished:

- 1) The site S requests all sites that have a copy of f for their values VN_i , SC_i , and DS_i . Let P denote the set consisting of the co-ordinator S and all the subordinates. Each subordinate locks its copy of the file f .
 - 2) The site S then calculates:
the value $M = \max\{VN_i : S_i \in P\}$,
and the set $I = \{S_j \in P : VN_j = M\}$.
- M denotes the largest version number which is in P , and the set I consists of those sites in P which have the version number M . S then takes the update site cardinality of *any* site in the set I . Denote this by N .
- 3) If $\text{card}(I)^\dagger > N/2$, then S is a member of a distinguished partition.
 - 4) Otherwise, if $\text{card}(I) = N/2$, then select any site S_j in I . (Any site in I will do; the choice is arbitrary.) If $DS_j \in I$, then S belongs to a distinguished partition.
 - 5) Otherwise, if $N = 3$, then the site S examines the value of the distinguished sites list DS_j of the site in I . (Since case 3 did not apply, there must be only a single site in I .) If P contains two or all three of the sites listed in DS_j , then also does S lie in a distinguished partition.
 - 6) Otherwise, S does not belong to a distinguished partition. In this case, the site S aborts the update, sends ABORT messages to the subordinates, and releases the lock on its copy. Upon receiving the abort message, the subordinates release all locks on their copies.

As we mentioned, a site S initiates the second phase if it has determined that it belongs to a distinguished partition. We continue to use the same notation as in the **Is_Distinguished** procedure.

Catch_Up:

All the sites in the set I possess the current copy of the file f , and the sites in the set $P - I$ have copies that are old. If the site S is not a member of the set I , it requests the missing updates from some site in I .

[†] In the algorithm, we have chosen to use locking instead of timestamps. It is easy to come up with a timestamp analog also.

[†] Notation: For a set X , $\text{card}(X)$ denotes its cardinality.

We note that at the end of this phase, the copy of f at the site S is current. Once this is done, the third and the final phase commences.

Do_Update:

- I) During this phase, the sites commit the update. The co-ordinator S commits the update to the file f and the new values for the three variables associated with each copy:

$$VN_i = M + 1$$

$$SC_i = \text{card}(P)$$

$$DS_i = \begin{cases} S' & \text{if } \text{card}(P) \text{ is even and } S' > S'' \\ & \text{for all } S'' \text{ in } P \\ P & \text{if } \text{card}(P) = 3 \end{cases}$$

except if $N = 3$ and $\text{card}(P) = 2$,

then there is no change made to SC_i and DS_i .

The site S sends to each subordinate the following: the COMMIT message, the new update to the file, and the new values for VN_i , SC_i , and DS_i . Also, S sends the missing updates to each subordinate in $P - I$. The site S then releases the lock on its copy of the file.

- II) Each subordinate upon receiving the message from S commits the update and unlocks its copy of the file.

Each time an update succeeds at a site, it commits the update together with the three values. Thus an update operation at a site is atomic in the sense that either all four operations—updates to the file, version number, update sites cardinality, and distinguished sites list—are performed in entirety or are not performed at all.

We should note that our protocol may cause deadlocks to occur. There are several ways to handle deadlocks, and we refer to the reader to [19] or [20] for additional details.

C. Protocol under failures

In this section, we describe how our protocol adjusts to site and communication link failures. We will describe a *restart protocol* which is executed by a site when it recovers from a failure.

Our restart protocol works as follows. When a site recovers from failure, it takes steps to ensure that its copy is brought up-to-date. We next describe how a site S can do this.

Make_Current:

- a) The site S locks its local copy and initiates execution of steps 1) - 5) of the procedure **Is-Distinguished** to determine if it is a member of a distinguished partition. The value M and the sets I and P are as described therein. Note that the subordinates in P lock their copies as well.
- b) If S is not in a distinguished partition, S sends ABORT messages to all the subordinates in P and

releases the lock on its local copy. (S cannot request missing updates from anyone; it may try again at a later time.) The subordinates upon receiving the ABORT message unlock their copies.

- c) If S does belong to a distinguished partition and the version number of the copy at S is equal to M , then the copy at S is current, and so S may skip the next step (the catch-up phase).
- d) If S belongs to a distinguished partition and the version number of the copy at S is less than M , then it requests the missing updates from any subordinate in the set I .
- e) Finally, S sends to all sites in P the COMMIT message, the missing updates (if necessary), the new version number which is now $M + 1$, the new update sites cardinality which is equal to $\text{card}(P)$, and possibly the new value for the distinguished sites list which is computed as follows: if $\text{card}(P) = 3$, then the new DS_i equals P ; and if $\text{card}(P)$ is even, then each DS_i takes on the value S' where $S' > S''$ for all S'' in P . Once this is done, S unlocks its local copy.
- f) The subordinates upon receiving the message from S commit the updates and unlock their copies.

We should note that whenever the **Make-Current** procedure permits an old copy to catch up, we treat this operation like an update in that we increment the version numbers of the participating copies by one.

It is straightforward to formulate a *termination protocol* which is invoked to correctly terminate transactions when the three-phase update procedure is interrupted by failures (see, for example [19, Chapter 7], or [20, Section 9.2.2.2]). Suppose S_i is a participant that has responded to a VOTE_REQUEST message to the co-ordinator, but has not received a COMMIT or ABORT message in return. In reply to any future VOTE_REQUEST, S_i sends the following values for its data structures: $VN_i = -\infty$, $SC_i = -\infty$, and $DS_i = -\infty$ where $-\infty$ is a value much smaller than any actual value for these variables. Now, S_i can correctly terminate the pending transaction in one of the following two ways: It can do so if it receives an offer from another site to join a majority partition or by executing the following termination protocol:

Termination_Protocol:

- 1) The *initiator* S_i sends a DECISION_REQUEST message to all sites. (Note that each update is uniquely identified by the id and the timestamp of the co-ordinator.)
- 2) A site S' upon receiving the DECISION_REQUEST message sends COMMIT to S_i if S' committed the update, sends ABORT to S_i if S' aborted the update, else does nothing.
- 3) If S_i receives a COMMIT or ABORT from *any* responder, it too can do likewise, else it must wait for some period of time and run this protocol again.

The above termination protocol can be modified into one that is more elaborate (see for example [20, Section 9.2.2.2]). The initiator S can further ask how many sites had responded to the VOTE_REQUEST message. If S determines that the sites that did not respond to the VOTE_REQUEST message form a distinguished partition, it can go ahead and abort the update.

Theorem. The hybrid algorithm is correct, i.e., maintains the consistency of the replicated file.

Proof. The proof is similar to the correctness proofs for dynamic voting [10] and dynamic-linear [11]. Details are available from the authors. \square

VI. AVAILABILITY OF THE HYBRID ALGORITHM

A. How should one evaluate the hybrid algorithm?

A sequence of failures, repairs, and update requests can occur in such a way that the hybrid algorithm can accommodate a request when other pessimistic algorithms cannot, and vice versa. To see this, consider the *partition graph* in Figure 1. It shows a five-node network that fragments into two partitions (ABC and DE) at time 1; partition ABC further fragments into AB and C at time 2; site C joins DE at time 3; etc. Suppose that at least one update arrives at each partition shortly after each partition change. Consider the behavior of voting, dynamic voting, dynamic-linear, and the hybrid algorithm on the network.

Figure 1. A partition graph for a file stored redundantly at sites A, B, C, D, and E.

At time 1, all four algorithms permit partition ABC to accept updates. At time 2, all the dynamic algorithms accept updates arriving at the AB partition. Voting, however, denies all updates at time 2. At time 3, CDE and A are the distinguished partitions for voting and dynamic-linear, respectively. (As before, we use lexicographic order to select the distinguished site for dynamic-linear and the

hybrid algorithm.) The other algorithms deny all updates at time 3. Note that if updates are distributed roughly uniformly over the sites, and if our performance measure is the fraction of updates that succeed (see Subsection C), then the performance of voting is strictly better than the performance of dynamic-linear at time 3, since voting's distinguished partition (CDE) is three times as large as dynamic-linear's distinguished partition (A). At time 4, only dynamic-linear and the hybrid algorithm permit updates. The hybrid algorithm performs better than dynamic-linear at time 4, since its distinguished partition (BC) is larger than the single-site distinguished partition for dynamic-linear.

The preceding example shows that at some times under some scenarios, one algorithm is best, while at other times under other scenarios another algorithm will be best. The real question is this: which algorithm is more *likely*, in the long run, to be able to handle any given update request? That is, which algorithm has greater *availability*?

B. The stochastic model

In this section we describe a stochastic model that makes precise what is meant by the phrase “more likely” in the preceding paragraph. The model is the same as that used previously to evaluate dynamic voting [10] and dynamic-linear [11]. The virtues and shortcomings of the model are discussed more fully in [10]. Here we simply remark that no one has yet obtained analytic results for dynamic algorithms from models any stronger than the model we describe here.

We make five assumptions to model stochastically the update availability of the network under dynamic algorithms. The first four assumptions duplicate assumptions that Pâris uses to analyze the availability of his *voting with witnesses* scheme [21]. The fifth assumption, however, causes our model to deviate from his.

- The communication links between sites are infallible. Only sites go up and down. Any site that is up can send a message to any other site that is up.
- The failures at the various sites form independent Poisson processes with uniform *failure rate* λ . For any given site that is up (functioning), the probability it goes down (fails) at or before the next t time units is $1 - e^{-\lambda t}$.
- Similarly, the repairs at the various sites form independent Poisson processes with uniform *repair rate* μ .
- Updates are instantaneous. We ignore communication delays in the three-phase protocol.
- Updates are frequent: after any failure or repair, an update always arrives at a functioning site and is processed before the next failure or repair. An alternative assumption that yields the same model is frequent polling: after any failure or repair, the functioning sites communicate to determine the new status of the system before the next failure or repair.

C. Two measures of availability

The standard measure of availability (see [22], [21], [8], and [23], for example) is the limit as t goes to infinity of the probability that a distinguished partition exists at time t , where the definition of “distinguished” depends on the algorithm used. An alternative measure is the limit as t goes to infinity of the probability that an update arriving at an arbitrary site at time t will succeed. This alternative measure requires not only that a distinguished partition exist, but also that the update arrive at a functioning site in the distinguished partition. The traditional measure is appropriate if updates are viewed as arriving to the *system*; the alternative measure is more appropriate if updates arrive at an individual *site*. In this report, we use the alternative measure, deeming it more appropriate for our application. Each formula in this paper requires only a trivial modification to use the standard measure.

D. The state diagram for the hybrid algorithm

The action of the hybrid algorithm is initially the same as that of dynamic voting. The system begins with all n sites in the distinguished partition. Eventually one site fails. Our fourth assumption insures that before another failure occurs or the failed site is repaired, an update arrives at a functioning site. The distinguished partition finds that it now contains $n-1$ of the n sites with up-to-date copies of the file—still a majority. The update sites cardinalities are adjusted to $n-1$ at the $n-1$ functioning sites. If a second failure then occurs, the distinguished partition will soon thereafter discover that it contains $n-2$ of the $n-1$ sites with up-to-date copies of the file—still a majority, so the update sites cardinalities will be adjusted to $n-2$ at the $n-2$ functioning sites. The process continues, with update site cardinalities always increasing or decreasing by one, until there are only three sites in the distinguished partition and a failure then occurs. Now the hybrid algorithm switches to its static phase. Although the subsequent update will be accepted, the update sites cardinality remains at three, with the distinguished sites list naming the three sites that form the distinguished partition, only two of which are currently functioning. Now if any site subsequently is repaired, the system will change the distinguished sites list to name the new trio of sites. Suppose instead that one of the two functioning sites fails, so that only a single site is now functioning. The subsequent update is blocked—one out of three sites is not a majority. Of these three sites in the most recent distinguished partition, call the one still up site U and the two down sites D_1 and D_2 . From this state, one of three events can occur.

- Site D_1 or D_2 might be repaired. The two-of-three distinguished partition is restored and the action of the network continues in the fashion described thus far.
- One or more of the other $n-3$ failed sites might be repaired. If sometime later site D_1 or D_2 is repaired and an update arrives, the functioning sites include two of the three sites on the distinguished sites list, hence a majority. In this case, however, the newly-formed distinguished partition will also include the other sites that have meanwhile been repaired.

- Site U might fail. Now two of the three sites U , D_1 , and D_2 must be repaired before a new distinguished partition will be formed. Again any such newly-formed distinguished partition will also include any other sites that have meanwhile been repaired.

The state diagram we have just described is shown in Figure 2. State (X, Y, Z) is the state in which:

- The update sites cardinality of each up-to-date copy of the file is Y .
- X of the Y sites with update sites cardinality Y are up.
- Z of the $n-Y$ other sites are up.

Arcs in the state diagram indicate the rate at which the system moves from state to state.

An update request will be accepted if it arrives at a functioning site and the network is in any of the states on the top row of Figure 2. Let A_2, A_3, \dots, A_n denote the steady-state probabilities of the top-row states, listed from left to right. Then the availability of the hybrid algorithm is

$$\sum_{k=2}^n \frac{k}{n} A_k$$

The $\frac{k}{n}$ term reflects the fact that the site at which the update request arrives must be one of the k functioning sites in state A_k .

To find the steady-state probabilities of the states in Figure 2, one sets the flow-out of each state equal to the flow-in to obtain the so-called *balance equations*, one equation per state. One of the $3n - 5$ equations thus obtained is redundant and can be replaced by the equation that says the probabilities sum to 1. It appears difficult to find a closed-form solution to this system of equations. However, for fixed n and fixed repair/failure ratio μ/λ , the system is easily solved by your favorite numerical technique for systems of linear equations. Furthermore, for fixed small values of n , the symbolic manipulator MACSYMATM can solve the system in terms of μ/λ .

E. Results

Theorem. The availability of the hybrid algorithm is greater than the availability of dynamic voting.

Proof. First consider the case when there are only three sites. Here the hybrid algorithm reduces to ordinary voting. Both voting and dynamic voting are available when all three sites are up. Neither is available when zero or one site is up. Voting is available if two of the three sites are up, but dynamic voting is more stringent: it requires that a *special* two sites be up, namely, the two sites that formed the most recent distinguished partition.

† MACSYMA is a trademark of Symbolics, Inc. It was originally developed by the Matlab Group of the MIT Laboratory for Computer Science.

Figure 2. The state diagram for the hybrid algorithm.

The argument for 4 or more sites requires that one embed the above argument into the network by using a dynamic site mapping. Details are available from the authors. \square

Dynamic-linear, dynamic voting, ordinary voting, and voting with a primary site have previously been compared under the stochastic model of this section [11]. Dynamic-linear has the most availability of these four algorithms, except when there are three sites; then ordinary voting has the greatest availability, except when the repair/failure ratio is small. We computed the availability of the hybrid algorithm for 3 to 20 sites, each time letting the repair/failure ratio vary from 0.1 to 20.0 in increments of 0.1. The following table summarizes the results of the comparison of the hybrid algorithm against dynamic-linear at those data points.

Hybrid > Dynamic-linear IF:

n = 3	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq .82$
n = 4	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq .67$
n = 5	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq .63$
n = 6	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq .64$
n = 7	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq .66$
n = 8	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq .70$
n = 9	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq .75$
n = 10	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq .81$
n = 11	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq .86$
n = 12	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq .92$
n = 13	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq .97$
n = 14	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq 1.01$
n = 15	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq 1.05$
n = 16	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq 1.08$
n = 17	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq 1.11$
n = 18	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq 1.14$
n = 19	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq 1.16$
n = 20	and	$\mu/\lambda \geq 1.19$

In sum, *the hybrid algorithm has greater availability than the dynamic-linear algorithm, and hence greater availability than voting, for all reasonable repair/failure ratios tested.*

Figures 3 and 4 display the above comparison graphically for a typical case: five sites. The repair/failure ratio varies from 0.1 to 2.0 in Figure 3, and from 2.0 to 10.0 in Figure 4. Each figure has curves for the hybrid algorithm, dynamic-linear and ordinary voting. Each curve is a graph of the *normalized availability* versus repair/failure ratio, where the normalized availability is

$$\text{availability} / \text{Prob (an arbitrary site is up)}.$$

No algorithm can have availability higher than the probability that an arbitrary site is up, given our non-traditional measure of availability. Hence figures 3 and 4 graph the performance of the algorithms as a fraction of the best performance possible.

Figure 3. Normalized availability for 5 sites; small repair/failure ratio

Figure 4. Normalized availability for 5 sites; big repair/failure ratio

VII. SUMMARY AND CHALLENGES

One can view the dynamic-linear algorithm as providing a practical means for dynamically reassigning votes: each participant in an update gets one vote, the distinguished site gets one extra vote (when the number of sites participating is even), and non-participants get no votes. Viewed this way, the dynamic-linear algorithm shows how very simple data structures (just three integers) can provide a practical means for accomplishing the group consensus method of dynamic vote reassignment suggested by Barbara, Garcia-Molina, and Spauster [8]. The hybrid algorithm goes one step further. It permits the sites to change algorithm in midstream: when three sites do an update, they halt the dynamic reassignment of votes until additional sites join the partition. If one of the three sites drops off, the two remaining sites still form a distinguished partition but choose to let the third site retain its vote.

The stochastic analysis of the hybrid algorithm shows that the hybrid algorithm has made a wise choice. For all reasonable repair/failure ratios, the availability of the hybrid algorithm exceeds that of its cousin algorithm, dynamic-linear. The price paid for this improvement is minimal: an integer variable must be converted to a triple of integer variables.

The hybrid algorithm presented in this paper is but one of many hybrids possible. The members of a distinguished partition may convert to any vote reassignment they choose (or more generally, any valid coterie [17,18]), so long as adequate data structures are provided. The hybrid algorithm in this paper is distinguished by the following conjecture.

Conjecture. Consider the model presented in Section VI. For each n (number of sites), there is a cross-over point $g(n)$ such that if the repair/failure ratio is less than $g(n)$, then dynamic-linear is the optimal algorithm, but otherwise the hybrid algorithm is the optimal algo-

rithm. By the *optimal* algorithm is meant the algorithm that provides greatest availability, taken over the class of all algorithms that insure the consistency of a replicated database in the face of network partitioning.

This conjecture, if true, would mean that the hybrid algorithm is the optimal algorithm for all reasonable repair/failure ratios. The uniformity of the model in section VI and the analytic results comparing dynamic-linear to voting provide good evidence for the conjecture. However, the enormity of the class of algorithms considered by the conjecture makes its proof an ambitious task.

There has been much work recently to establish the optimal *static* assignment of votes or coterie in various heterogeneous models and to find heuristics that approach this optimum [17,18,24,23,25]. These are models which lack symmetry in communication links and uniformity in repair/failure ratios. The existence of practical dynamic algorithms provides a greater challenge: what is the optimal *dynamic* assignment of votes in such heterogeneous models, and what heuristics approach this optimum?

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